

Orbital Logistics: Optimal Planning to Service Multiple Satellites in LEO through Mixed Integer Linear Programming and Q-law

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ORBITAL LOGISTICS: OPTIMAL PLANNING TO SERVICE MULTIPLE SATELLITES IN LEO THROUGH MIXED INTEGER LINEAR PROGRAMMING AND Q-LAW

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This paper addresses the problem of finding the optimal visiting sequence and trajectory for a servicer satellite that has to visit multiple client satellite once, minimizing fuel spent and satisfying the Keplerian dynamics and low-thrust propulsion system constraints. The cost of each transfer is evaluated through two different cost functions: an approximated analytical cost function based on Edelbaum's theory and a more accurate Q-law cost function. The optimal sequence is found by using an Exhaustive Search algorithm and a Mixed Integer Linear Programming. Computational time and accuracy of the methods are compared. In all cases the global optimum is obtained. In particular, the implementation of the Q-law cost function in the Mixed Integer Linear Programming context provides the optimal sequence for a large dataset while maintaining accurate trajectory estimation.

INTRODUCTION

On-orbit Servicing Assembly and Manufacturing (OSAM) Missions¹ are drawing increasing attention. In particular, an OSAM mission to serve multiple satellites involves multiple rendezvous maneuvers between the servicing satellite and the client satellites. Problems of this kind, referred to as "*Moving-Target (or time-dependent) Travelling Salesman Problems*" (MTTSP), turn out to be NP-complete² and involve the choice of the optimal visiting sequence of the clients which are subject to orbital dynamics (moving targets). A cost (propellant, time or a combination of the two³) is associated to each individual visiting maneuver (leg); the optimal sequence coincides with the sequence whose sum of cost of all legs is the lowest possible. The optimization problem consists of a mixed integer/continuous variables problem. MTTSP can be split into two sub-problems:

1. Generation of the sequence of clients to visit
2. Evaluation of the cost of each maneuver (*distance metric or leg cost function*)

The choice of both the algorithm generating the sequence and the cost function adopted to quantify the cost of each maneuver is dependent on the orbital dynamics model used to propagate the satellites trajectories, the servicer propulsion system characteristics and the dataset size.

A crucial aspect of the problem is represented by the way the cost of each leg is quantified. In order to obtain the global minimum, the maneuver enabling the rendezvous between the servicer and a client should be derived relying on optimality conditions. For example, if the goal is to find the visiting sequence which minimizes fuel spent by the servicer, the cost in terms of fuel of each leg has to be derived considering an optimal control law obtained in the minimum-fuel context.

Many authors have presented solutions for the case of high-thrust propulsion system.³⁻⁶ In case of a great

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number of clients, fuel consumption required by high-thrust propulsion systems can become impractical. If a long mission is tolerated, low-thrust propulsion systems allow reduced fuel consumption, representing an appropriate technology for multiple-visitation missions. In the context of low-thrust propulsion, the use of optimal computational methodologies, based on Direct Methods (DM) or Indirect Methods (IM)⁷ Optimization, for the evaluation of the cost associated with the individual leg would be the most natural. These methods succeed in finding the optimal solution but can present some problems such as a restricted convergence domain (especially for IM), the need of an accurate first guess (for DM)⁸ and, in general, a relatively high computational cost that makes their application to the MTTSP prohibitive (because of the large number of possible sequences to be evaluated). Therefore, it is necessary to have even sub-optimal but faster methodologies to deal with the problem.

Several sub-optimal low-thrust solutions exist in particular cases and they often make assumptions in order to obtain the solution in closed form.^{7,9-11} Main assumptions concern the perturbations included in the dynamics model, consideration of true anomaly targeting (phasing maneuver), type of propulsion system (Constant Specific Impulse (CSI) or Variable Specific Impulse (VSI)⁷), fuel mass depletion or constant acceleration, constraints due to eclipse or particular strategies employed (i.e., inclusion of drift orbits to minimize fuel for RAAN correction), minimum-time or minimum-fuel (fixed final time or free final time) frameworks. The other key aspect regards the sequence optimization. The algorithms for sequence optimization can be divided into two main subgroups: Deterministic and Heuristic algorithms. Deterministic algorithms find the global optimum and are usually employed for small datasets. An example of this kind of algorithms is given by Exhaustive Search (ES) (or "Brute Force") which returns the global minimum by evaluating the sequence cost for all possible sequences. A high computational burden is associated with Deterministic algorithms which become impractical when a large dataset is considered. To obtain a feasible solution within reasonable computational time, Heuristic algorithms (e.g., Greedy Algorithm,¹² Genetic Algorithm,¹³ Simulated Annealing,¹⁴ etc) introduce probability functions for the creation of the sequences to evaluate. Their accuracy depends on user-defined parameters and the global optimality is not assured.

Many authors have tried to simplify the problem in order to obtain a feasible solution in a reasonable amount of time. Damaren¹⁵ finds the optimal sequence of a multiple-visitation problem by adopting a simple distance metric (only inclination and RAAN differences between satellites are considered) similar to that employed by Izzo et al.¹⁶ The sequence so found is then propagated by Q-law¹⁷ in order to obtain fuel consumption and trajectories. Zuiani et al.¹⁸ solves a bi-objective MTTSP for a five debris removal mission. Their model uses averaged dynamical equations and neglects the phasing maneuver cost. The distance metric accounts for five-element targeting and can be evaluated quickly by functions derived by interpolation of pre-computed results. The optimal sequence is found by using an Heuristic algorithm multiple times. Di Carlo et al.¹⁹ establishes a surrogate low-thrust transfer model accounting for J_2 secular perturbation which is not based on optimal control theory. Li et al.²⁰ derives an analytic distance metric accounting for three orbital elements targeting for minimum-time transfer. Minimum-fuel case is also derived through empirical formulas. The approach considers J_2 secular perturbation and optimal sequence trajectory is obtained through indirect optimization methods.

In this paper, a new algorithm combining Q-law with MILP is proposed for the first time to the best knowledge of the authors. The proposed QL/MILP algorithm is able to efficiently obtain the minimum-fuel sequence for five-orbital-element multiple orbit transfers, with the assumption of Keplerian dynamics. The same results in terms of optimal sequence are obtained with respect to Exhaustive Search.

MOVING TARGET TSP (MTTSP) PROBLEM STATEMENT

From a mathematical point of view, the MTTSP belongs to combinatorial problems where both integer and continuous variables have to be optimized.²¹ Integer variables are used to represent each of the possible visiting sequences: a sequence can be defined by the ordered vector $\mathbf{d} = [d_1, \dots, d_{N_{sat}}]$ whose components are the IDs of the N_{sat} satellites to be visited. On the other hand, continuous variables are used to represent the vector $\mathbf{T}_F = [t_1, \dots, t_{N_{sat}}]$ containing the time of each rendezvous. In its general form, the MTTSP can be stated as follows

MTTSP Problem Statement

$$J_D = \min_{\mathbf{d}, \mathbf{T}_F} \left(C_0(d_1, t_0, t_1) + \sum_{i=1}^{N_{sat}-1} C_i(d_i, d_{i+1}, t_i, t_{i+1}) \right)$$

subject to

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{X}}(t) &= \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{X}(t), \mathbf{T}(t)) & \forall t \in [0, t_{N_{sat}}] \\ \dot{\mathbf{X}}_i(t) &= \mathbf{G}_i(\mathbf{X}_i(t), \mathbf{T}_i(t)) & \forall t \in [0, t_{N_{sat}}], i = 1, \dots, N_{sat} \\ \mathbf{X}(t_0) &= \mathbf{X}_0 \\ \mathbf{X}_i(t_0) &= \mathbf{X}_{i,0} & i = 1, \dots, N_{sat} \\ \underline{\mathbf{X}}_{[1:6]}(t_i) &= \underline{\mathbf{X}}_{d_i, [1:6]}(t_i) & i = 1, \dots, N_{sat} \\ \mathbf{Z}_{eq}(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}_1, \dots, \mathbf{X}_{N_{sat}}, \mathbf{T}_F) &= 0 \\ \mathbf{Z}_{ineq}(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{X}_1, \dots, \mathbf{X}_{N_{sat}}, \mathbf{T}_F) &\leq 0 \end{aligned}$$

where $C_0(d_1, t_0, t_1)$ represents the cost of going from the initial servicer orbit at time t_0 to satellite d_1 at time t_1 , while in general $C_i(d_i, d_{i+1}, t_i, t_{i+1})$ represents the cost of going from satellite d_i at time t_i to satellite d_{i+1} at time t_{i+1} . Furthermore, $\mathbf{X}(t)$ represents the state of the servicer, consisting of the Keplerian Elements and the current mass, $\mathbf{X}(t) = [a(t), e(t), i(t), \Omega(t), \omega(t), \theta(t), m(t)]$; and $\mathbf{X}_i(t)$ the state of the i -th client. \mathbf{F} and \mathbf{G}_i represent respectively the dynamics of the servicer and the dynamics of i -th client; they are functions of the state and of the control thrust acting on the satellite ($\mathbf{T}(t)$ or $\mathbf{T}_i(t)$). \mathbf{X}_0 and $\mathbf{X}_{i,0}$ are the initial boundary conditions, while $\underline{\mathbf{X}}_{[1:6]}(t_i) = \underline{\mathbf{X}}_{d_i, [1:6]}(t_i)$ are the rendezvous conditions between the servicer and the client, the subscript $[1 : 6]$ underlines that only the first six components of the state have to be the same at time t_i . Finally, \mathbf{Z}_{eq} and \mathbf{Z}_{ineq} represent other non-linear equality or inequality constraints which can involve the states of the satellites and/or time of flights. The problem is intrinsically time-dependent. The satellites are subject to dynamics; if perturbations are included into the propagation model (e.g., J_2 , drag) the orbits of clients change over time. In addition, servicer fuel mass depletion causes an increment of acceleration, at the same thrust, over time. Finally, rendezvous constraints $\underline{\mathbf{X}}_{[1:6]}(t_i) = \underline{\mathbf{X}}_{i, [1:6]}(t_i)$ impose that the servicer and each client must have the same orbital elements (or, equivalently, same absolute position and velocity) at time t_i . In general, the problem stated above, is difficult to solve, not only for the reasons mentioned above but also for the size of the dataset used. In particular, the number of possible sequences is $N_{sat}!$ further more the computation of the cost of each leg expensive.

FROM MTTSP TO STATIC TSP DEFINITION

The following assumptions are imposed to reduce the MTTSP to a Static TSP (STSP).

1. Constraints

Additional equality and inequality constraints \mathbf{Z}_{eq} and \mathbf{Z}_{ineq} are neglected.

2. Perturbations

Perturbations are neglected. All satellites are subjected only to Keplerian Dynamics.

3. Rendezvous Cost

Phasing cost is neglected. The cost difference between a transfer maneuver and a rendezvous maneuver is generally negligible.²²

4. Servicer Fuel Mass Depletion

Fuel mass depletion is neglected. Given a maximum thrust level (T_{max}), it is easier to transfer a satellite with a lower mass. This aspect can change the selection of next satellite to visit and the overall optimal sequence. One of the possible criteria to choose an optimal sequence is the minimization of the fuel consumption used to visit all the clients. Assuming no gravitational losses, fuel consumption can be obtained from the transfer cost quantified in terms of ΔV through the Tsiolkowsky equation

$\Delta m = m_0(1 - e^{-\frac{\Delta V}{g_0 I_{sp}}})$ where m_0 is the fuel of the satellite before the maneuver, $g_0 = 9.80655[m/s^2]$ is a constant and I_{sp} is the specific impulse of the propulsion system. With this assumption, minimizing the overall ΔV is equal to minimizing the fuel consumption. It is important to underline that the time of flight to perform a transfer maneuver strictly depends on the adopted propulsion system. Time of flight of each leg is correlated to the optimal sequence solution in the MTTSP. In the static case, where orbits to visit are fixed and phasing cost is neglected, the minimum ΔV of each possible leg does not depend on time but only on the characteristics of initial and final orbits. This is due to the fact that targeted orbital elements $(a, e, i, \Omega, \omega)$ are not function of time and fixed in the state space; consequently, the minimum ΔV required to pass from a point in the state space to another is not dependent on time. Both the mass depletion and time of flight can be then computed from the characteristics of the propulsion system and do not influence the selection of next client to visit. Next sections will focus on the minimization of the ΔV as the criteria to chose the optimal tour.

In addition to these 4 assumptions, we leave to consider the servicer embedded with low-thrust propulsion. After presenting and discussing the assumptions to eliminate time dependencies, a mathematical definition of the STSP can be given

STSP Problem Statement

$$J_S = \min_{\mathbf{d}} J(\mathbf{d}) = \min_{\mathbf{d}} \left(C_0(d_1) + \sum_{i=1}^{N_{sat}-1} C_i(d_i, d_{i+1}) \right)$$

subject to

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{X}}(t) &= \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{X}(t), \mathbf{T}(t)) & \forall t \in [0, t_{N_{sat}}] \\ \mathbf{X}(t_0) &= \mathbf{X}_0 \\ \mathbf{X}_i(t) &= \mathbf{X}_{i,0} & \forall t \in [0, t_{N_{sat}}], i = 1, \dots, N_{sat} \\ \mathbf{X}(t_i) &= \mathbf{X}_{d_i}(t_i) & i = 1, \dots, N_{sat} \end{aligned}$$

where $C_0(d_1)$ represents the cost of going from the initial servicer orbit to satellite d_1 , while $C_i(d_i, d_{i+1})$ represents the cost of going from satellite d_i to satellite d_{i+1} . $\mathbf{X}(t_0)$ represents the state of the servicer at initial time t_0 and does not consider the angular position and mass, for example, using Keplerian Elements $\mathbf{X}(t_0) = [a(t_0), e(t_0), i(t_0), \Omega(t_0), \omega(t_0)]$ and $\mathbf{X}_i(t)$ that of the i -th client which is considered fixed $\forall t$. The constraint $\mathbf{X}(t_i) = \mathbf{X}_{d_i}(t_i)$ underlines that the five orbital elements of the servicer and client d_i have to be the same at time t_i . Since perturbations are not included and angular position is neglected, $\mathbf{X}_{d_i}(t_i) = \mathbf{X}_{d_i}(t_0)$ does not introduce a time dependency. These assumptions make the vector of time of flights \mathbf{T}_F only dependent on the sequence \mathbf{d} ($\mathbf{T}_F = \mathbf{T}_F(\mathbf{d})$) thus leaving only the vector \mathbf{d} as the optimization variable. In particular, the transfer time of the i -th leg (t_i) is a direct consequence of the propulsion system of the servicer and the distance metric adopted. Finally, it is possible to remark that during each transfer the servicer can be still subject to the dynamics \mathbf{F} ; this factor will be taken into account by the distance metric employed thus not inducing additional time dependency (this aspect will be better clarified in the following sections). The problem consists now in finding the sequence which minimizes J_S . Once the distance metric is chosen, the total cost will depend only on the sequence and the initial orbital elements thus reducing the search space (\mathbf{T}_F is not present) and the problem to an Integer Problem. In the following sections, the distance metrics adopted in this paper and algorithms to solve STSP are presented.

DISTANCE METRICS

Improved Edelbaum $\Delta V_{Ed, \Omega}$

Edelbaum's pionieristic work⁹ reports the ΔV required to transfer a satellite between two circular orbits which differ only for inclination and semi-major axes. The result considers only the central body perturbation, averaged dynamics equations, constant control acceleration, only tangential and out-of plane thrust

components in the minimum-time context. This distance metric results are quite accurate when near-circular orbits with the same RAAN are considered. While it is usually possible to find clusters of possible satellites to visit with similar semi-major axis, inclinations and low eccentricities, it cannot be assumed in general that they have similar RAANs. As documented in Reference 9, inclination and RAAN change maneuvers are the most expensive; thus, it is essential to have a distance metric which accounts for RAAN correction. Reference 7 improved Edelbaum's solution in order to account for the RAAN targeting. The solution is found in terms of ΔV in the minimum-time context adopting similar assumptions of Reference 9 and splitting the transfer into two phases, the first correcting the velocity difference (which, for circular orbits, is equivalent to semi-major axis correction) and the inclination $((V, i))$ and the second correcting the velocity and the RAAN $((V, \Omega))$. Reference 7 also presented an alternative strategy where the two phases are performed in the opposite way (i.e., (V, Ω) and (V, i)). Reference 23 uses these results and combines the two strategies to find a $\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}$ expression accounting for simultaneous correction of velocity, inclination and RAAN. The ΔV can be quantified as

$$\begin{aligned}\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega} &= \Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}(d_i, d_j) = \sqrt{V_{d_i}^2 + V_{d_j}^2 - 2V_{d_i}V_{d_j} \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2}g(i_{d_i}, i_{d_j}, \Omega_{d_i}, \Omega_{d_j})\right)} \\ g(i_{d_i}, i_{d_j}, \Omega_{d_i}, \Omega_{d_i}) &= \sqrt{\Delta i^2 + \sin^2(\bar{i})\Delta\Omega^2}\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

where d_i and d_j indicate the IDs of the initial and final orbits, $V_{d_i} = \sqrt{\mu/a_{d_i}}$ and $V_{d_j} = \sqrt{\mu/a_{d_j}}$ are their orbital velocity magnitudes of the corresponding circular orbits (the eccentricity is neglected), $\Delta i = i_{d_j} - i_{d_i}$, $\Delta\Omega = \Omega_{d_j} - \Omega_{d_i}$ and $\bar{i} = (i_{d_j} + i_{d_i})/2$ is the mean inclination. Equation 1 accounts only for three orbital elements targeting (a, e, Ω) in minimum-time framework and neglects the fuel mass depletion during the transfer. In addition, its symmetric nature ($\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}(d_i, d_j) = \Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}(d_j, d_i)$) makes it suitable for the MILP algorithm presented in the next sections.

Q-law based ΔV_{QL}

Q-law Overview

Q-law is a closed-loop feedback-driven (CLFD) guidance method first proposed by Petropoulos.¹⁷ It is based on Lyapunov's second theorem²⁴ which affirms that for a system represented by the dynamics $\dot{\mathbf{Z}} = \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{Z})$ (where $\mathbf{Z} = \mathbf{X} - \mathbf{X}_T$, \mathbf{X} is the state and \mathbf{X}_T is a target state), \mathbf{X}_T is a globally asymptotically stable point of the state space if there exist a scalar function $Q(\mathbf{Z})$ such that $Q(\mathbf{0}) = 0$; it is positive-definite ($Q(\mathbf{Z}) > 0, \forall \mathbf{Z} \neq \mathbf{0}$); its time derivative is $\dot{Q}(\mathbf{Z}) < 0, \forall \mathbf{Z} \neq \mathbf{0}$ and $\lim_{\|\mathbf{Z}\| \rightarrow \infty} Q(\mathbf{Z}) = \infty$. Considering its application to space trajectories, the state can be represented by orbital elements; if Keplerian elements are used, the state (neglecting the fast variable) is $\mathbf{X}(t) = [a(t), e(t), i(t), \Omega(t), \omega(t)]$, its time derivative is $\dot{\mathbf{X}}(t) = \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{X}(t))\mathbf{u}(t)$ where $\mathbf{B} \in \mathcal{R}^{[5 \times 3]}$ is a matrix representing the Gauss Variational Equations and $\mathbf{u}(t) = \mathbf{T}(t)/m(t)$ is the vector of control acceleration. In this case, it is possible to write the time derivative of the general Lyapunov function $Q(\mathbf{Z})$ as

$$\dot{Q}(\mathbf{Z}) = \frac{\partial Q(\mathbf{Z})}{\partial t} = \frac{\partial Q(\mathbf{Z})}{\partial \mathbf{X}} \dot{\mathbf{X}} = \frac{\partial Q(\mathbf{Z})}{\partial \mathbf{X}} \mathbf{B}(\mathbf{X})\mathbf{u}\quad (2)$$

For a given Lyapunov function, it is possible to obtain near-optimal minimum-time trajectories by minimizing its time derivative at each instant by choosing

$$\mathbf{u} = -\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{X})^T \frac{\partial Q(\mathbf{Z})}{\partial \mathbf{X}}\quad (3)$$

Equation 3 automatically satisfies one of the necessary conditions presented above because it guarantees that $\dot{Q}(\mathbf{Z}) < 0, \forall \mathbf{Z} \neq \mathbf{0}$ (except when $e = 0, i = 0, i = \pi$ because $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{X})$ becomes singular). Ref. 4 proposes the

following Lyapunov function

$$Q(\mathbf{X}) = (1 + W_P P) \sum_{i=1}^5 W_i S_i \left(\frac{\delta X_i}{\max_{\theta}(\dot{X}_i)} \right)^2, \quad \delta \mathbf{X} = \begin{bmatrix} a - a_T \\ e - e_T \\ i - i_T \\ a \cos(\cos(\Omega - \Omega_T)) \\ a \cos(\cos(\omega - \omega_T)) \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

where subscript T denotes the target value. $W_P, W_{[1:5]}$ are user defined parameters and could be adjusted in order to prioritize the convergence of a particular element; they could be optimized to obtain better results in terms of speed of convergence and accuracy, P and $S_{[1:5]}$ are predefined functions and $\max_{\theta}(\dot{X}_i)$ is the maximum rate of change of $i - th$ orbital element with respect to true anomaly over the current osculating orbit and can be calculated analytically for all elements except for ω in case of Keplerian dynamics. The analytic expressions of these terms are reported in Reference 17. From Equations 4 it is possible to compute the analytic form of $\partial Q(\mathbf{Z})/\partial \mathbf{X}$ and from Equation 3 the control acceleration at each instant by using the osculating orbital elements. It is sufficient to integrate the system starting with initial orbital elements using the near-optimal control in order to drive the satellite to the target; the integration is stopped when $\|\delta X_i\| \leq \epsilon_i, \forall i = 1, \dots, 5$ where ϵ_i is the $i - th$ orbital element predefined tolerance. Considering the results coming from the application of Pontryagin's Minimum Principle for the minimum-time space trajectories²⁵ in the case of a Constant Specific Impulse (CSI) propulsion system (i.e., the optimal trajectory is composed by maximum-thrust-always-on arcs), it is possible to rewrite the control acceleration as

$$\mathbf{u} = \frac{T_{max}}{m} \begin{bmatrix} \sin(\alpha) \cos(\beta) \\ \cos(\alpha) \cos(\beta) \\ \sin(\beta) \end{bmatrix} \quad (5)$$

where T_{max} is the maximum available thrust, α and β are respectively the tangential and the out-of-plane angles of the thrust. Implementing Equation 5, Q-law emulates the optimal solution. The time of flight and the fuel depletion are a direct consequence of the weights and the stopping criteria. Several works present methods to adjust these user defined parameters in order to obtain better results.²⁶ These algorithms can rely on the fast computation of the Q-law trajectory but their additional computational time would be too expensive for their application in TSP problems. When the minimization of the fuel is the target of the optimization problem, for CSI propulsion systems Pontryagin's Minimum Principle applied to space trajectories states that the solution is composed by maximum-thrust-arcs and thrust-off-arcs (coast arcs).⁷ Previous derivation of the Q-law did not consider a mechanism to switch the thrust off. A switch-off strategy is presented in Reference 17; two additional parameters, the so-called relative and absolute effectivities (η_r and η_a), are defined. These parameters introduce coast arcs at points where the engine thrust is less efficient, they are defined as

$$\eta_a = \frac{\min_{\alpha, \beta}(\dot{Q})}{\min_{\theta}(\min_{\alpha, \beta}(\dot{Q}))}, \quad \eta_r = \frac{\min_{\alpha, \beta}(\dot{Q}) - \max_{\theta}(\min_{\alpha, \beta}(\dot{Q}))}{\min_{\theta}(\min_{\alpha, \beta}(\dot{Q})) - \max_{\theta}(\min_{\alpha, \beta}(\dot{Q}))} \quad (6)$$

where $\min_{\alpha, \beta}(\dot{Q})$ is the minimum of the Lyapunov function with respect to α and β evaluated at the osculating orbital elements (including anomaly) and can be computed using Equation 3 as

$$\min_{\alpha, \beta}(\dot{Q}) = \min_{\alpha, \beta} \left(\left(\frac{\partial Q}{\partial \mathbf{X}} \right) \mathbf{B} \mathbf{u} \right) = - \left\| \mathbf{B}^T \left(\frac{\partial Q}{\partial \mathbf{X}} \right)^T \right\|$$

while $\min_{\theta}(\min_{\alpha, \beta}(\dot{Q}))$ and $\max_{\theta}(\min_{\alpha, \beta}(\dot{Q}))$ are respectively the minimum and the maximum of the time derivative of the Lyapunov function with respect to α, β and θ over an entire orbit ($\theta \in [0, 2\pi]$); these quantities can not be expressed in closed form and they have to be obtained numerically (for example through a grid search algorithm). η_r and η_a attempt to quantify the effectiveness in changing the orbital parameters at a given osculating point compared to the optimum point for changing the orbital parameters over a complete orbit. When some thresholds are set ($\bar{\eta}_r, \bar{\eta}_a$), the control law follows

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{u} &= \mathbf{0} && \text{if } \eta_r \leq \bar{\eta}_r \text{ or } \eta_a \leq \bar{\eta}_a \\ \mathbf{u} &= \frac{T_{max}}{m} \begin{bmatrix} \sin(\alpha) \cos(\beta) \\ \cos(\alpha) \cos(\beta) \\ \sin(\beta) \end{bmatrix} && \text{otherwise} \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

This strategy emulates the results of Minimum Principle in the context of minimum-fuel optimization. As the minimum-time case, the time of flight of the transfer is a consequence of parameters and stopping criteria. Q-law cannot be used in any of its forms where the time of flight is prescribed. It is important to underline that Q-law can include main perturbations (secular J_2 , drag, eclipse) maintaining the same form for the control acceleration (i.e., perturbations are not included into $\mathbf{B}(\mathbf{X})$) but using the osculating orbital elements coming from the propagation of the perturbed dynamics.²⁷ Q-law has been also reformulated for Equinoctial Elements²⁸ or for six elements targeting.^{15,29} These variations are under investigation for their possible use in the MTTSP.

Q-law Based Distance Metric

Once the servicer initial mass m_0 and the characteristics of its propulsion system are defined (T_{max}, I_{sp}), Q-law computes the mass history $m(t)$ and the final transfer time t_f . Fuel mass depletion can be computed as $\Delta m = m_0 - m(t_f)$ and represents a possible distance metric. In multiple visitation problems, the variation of the servicer mass would introduce a sequence dependency thus an alternative approach is needed. A possible way to bypass this sequence dependency consists in using Q-law cost estimation in terms of ΔV which, in Keplerian dynamics, only depends on initial and final orbital elements and strategy (minimum-time or minimum-fuel). For a generic transfer from d_i to d_j orbit, Q-law can provide the mass of the servicer as function of time $m_{d_i \rightarrow d_j}(t)$ and the so-called switching function $B_{d_i \rightarrow d_j}(t)$ ($B_{d_i \rightarrow d_j}(t) = 1$ if the thrust is on at instant t , while $B_{d_i \rightarrow d_j}(t) = 0$ otherwise). From mass and switching histories, it is possible to compute the increment in velocity $\Delta V_{QL}(d_i, d_j)$ and the Duty Cycle $DC_{QL}(d_i, d_j)$ through the following integrals

$$\Delta V_{QL}(d_i, d_j) = \int_{t_{0,d_i}}^{t_{f,d_i \rightarrow d_j}} \frac{T_{max}}{m_{d_i \rightarrow d_j}(t)} B_{d_i \rightarrow d_j}(t) dt \quad (8)$$

$$DC_{QL}(d_i, d_j) = \frac{1}{t_{f,d_i \rightarrow d_{i+1}}} \int_{t_{0,d_i}}^{t_{f,d_i \rightarrow d_j}} B_{d_i \rightarrow d_j}(t) dt \quad (9)$$

where T_{max} is the maximum available thrust, t_{0,d_i} is the initial transfer time when servicer departs from d_i - *th* orbit while $t_{f,d_i \rightarrow d_j}$ is the time of flight returned by the convergence of the Q-law. It is evident that in case of minimum-time context, $DC_{d_i \rightarrow d_j} = 1$ since $B_{d_i \rightarrow d_j}(t) = 1, \forall t \in [t_{0,d_i}, t_{f,d_i \rightarrow d_j}]$, while in case of minimum-fuel context, the Duty Cycle depends on relative and absolute effectiveness thresholds ($\bar{\eta}_r$ and $\bar{\eta}_a$). Considering the assumptions presented in previous sections, it is also true that $\Delta V_{QL}(d_i, d_j) = \Delta V_{QL}(d_j, d_i)$ and $DC_{QL}(d_i, d_j) = DC_{QL}(d_j, d_i)$. ΔV_{QL} has similar properties with respect to $\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}$ making a comparison of the results straightforward.

ALGORITHMS TO SOLVE STSP

In this section, the methods applied to solve the STSP will be presented in detail. Indicating with the term *leg* the generic transfer between two orbits, $\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}$ and ΔV_{QL} functions have been used as distance metrics to quantify the cost of each leg in terms of propellant. The ultimate goal is to find the sequence of satellites to visit which minimizes the total cost (i.e., sum of selected legs).

Exhaustive Search (ES)

Exhaustive Search is the simplest and most intuitive algorithm for solving the STSP. It consists in enumerating all possible sequences, evaluating the total cost corresponding to each of them, and choosing the sequence

which has the minimum cost. If $\mathbf{D} = [\mathbf{d}_1^T, \dots, \mathbf{d}_{N_{sat}!}^T]$ represents the matrix containing all possible sequences ($N_{sat}!$ is the number of possible sequence permutations to visit N_{sat} clients) and $\mathbf{J} = [J(\mathbf{d}_1), \dots, J(\mathbf{d}_{N_{sat}!})]$ is the vector containing the cost of each sequence, the solution is $\mathbf{d}_{opt} = \mathbf{d} : \min \mathbf{J} = [J(\mathbf{d}_1), \dots, J(\mathbf{d}_{N_{sat}!})]$. The algorithm finds the global optimum because it iterates over all possible sequences but it is computationally inefficient. Two main problems are associated to the enumeration of the sequences. The first is linked to memory problems; in fact, saving all possible sequences into matrix \mathbf{D} can cause the saturation of the RAM. It is possible to solve this problem by avoiding to save all the sequence and creating the next sequence starting from the previous with an iterative procedure. The second problem is linked to the computational time needed to evaluate a single sequence. In the following sections, this aspect will be detailed showing how ES becomes prohibitively expensive even when analytic distance metrics are employed.

Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP)

Mixed Integer Linear Programming (MILP)³⁰ is a computationally efficient method to find the solution of problems involving linear cost and linear constraints. The optimization variables can be either continuous or constrained to be integers. In its most general form, the problem solved by MILP solvers can be written as follows

MILP Problem Definition

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{\mathbf{x}} \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{x} \\ & \text{subject to} \\ & \mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{N}^m \\ & \mathbf{x}_{lb} \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{x}_{ub} \\ & \mathbf{A}_{eq} \mathbf{x} = \mathbf{b}_{eq} \\ & \mathbf{A}_{ineq} \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{b}_{ineq} \end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbf{x} = [x_1, \dots, x_m]$ is the vector containing the optimization variables, \mathbf{w} is the vector containing the costs associated to each optimization variable (it does not depend on \mathbf{x}), \mathbf{x}_{lb} and \mathbf{x}_{ub} are the boundary constraints of the optimization variables, $\mathbf{A}_{eq} \in \mathcal{R}^{l \times m}$ and $\mathbf{b}_{eq} \in \mathcal{R}^l$ are respectively the equality constraints matrix and vector, $\mathbf{A}_{ineq} \in \mathcal{R}^{p \times m}$ and $\mathbf{b}_{ineq} \in \mathcal{R}^p$ represent the inequality constraints matrix and vector. A problem of this kind can be quickly solved by using efficient LP-based solvers. In general, they firstly solve an initial relaxed non-integer problem using Linear Programming, perform a Mixed-Integer Program pre-processing to tighten the relaxation, use *Cut Generation* to further tighten the LP relaxation of the mixed-integer problem, find integer-feasible solutions using heuristics and finally use a Branch and Bound algorithm to search for the optimal solution.³¹ Not all the problems can be written in the MILP form. If the problem is intrinsically convex, constructing valid MILP formulations is relatively straightforward; on the contrary, if the problem presents non-linearities, some manipulations are needed to try to convexify the cost function and/or the constraints in order to obtain a suitable form for the MILP solver. Focusing on the STSP definition, as the problem is not dependent on time nor on previously visited satellites, it is possible to consider the following optimization variable \mathbf{x} and cost vector \mathbf{w}

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{x} &= [x_{0 \rightarrow 1}, \dots, x_{0 \rightarrow N_{sat}}, x_{1 \rightarrow 2}, \dots, x_{1 \rightarrow N_{sat}}, \dots, x_{N_{sat}-1 \rightarrow N_{sat}}]^T \\ \mathbf{w} &= [w_{0 \rightarrow 1}, \dots, w_{0 \rightarrow N_{sat}}, w_{1 \rightarrow 2}, \dots, w_{1 \rightarrow N_{sat}}, \dots, w_{N_{sat}-1 \rightarrow N_{sat}}]^T \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where the subscripts $0, 1, \dots, N_{sat}$ denote the IDs of the orbits, 0 is the ID related to the initial service orbit, while the general component of the optimization vector $x_{i \rightarrow j} \in [0, 1]$ takes the value of 1 if the transfer from i -th orbit to j -th is performed (i.e., selection of the $i \rightarrow j$ leg) and 0 otherwise. $w_{i \rightarrow j} \in \mathcal{R}^+$ represents the cost associated with the transfer starting from i -th to j -th orbit. This definition assumes that the cost matrix is symmetric (i.e., $w_{i \rightarrow j} = w_{j \rightarrow i}$). This assumption is automatically satisfied when the time and sequence dependencies are neglected and the ΔV is used as distance metric. The case of asymmetric cost can be easily handled by including further optimization variables which consider the opposite transfers

(i.e., $x_{j \rightarrow i}$ opposite transfer of $x_{i \rightarrow j}$ and so on). In this case, the size of the search space would increase thus slowing the convergence of the MILP solver. Focusing on the symmetric cost matrix case, it remains to define lower and upper boundaries, and equality and inequality constraints. The size of the optimization vector is $S = (N_{sat} + 1)! / ((N_{sat} - 1)!2!) = (N_{sat} + 1)N_{sat}/2$ drastically reducing the complexity linked to ES algorithm where the sequences to evaluate were $N_{sat}!$. Equations 10 allow for a graph representation of the problem where the nodes of the graph represent all the orbits of the dataset and the edges connecting them represent the selected transfer maneuvers. The graph visualization makes easier the conceptual derivation of equality and inequality constraints. Recalling that the problem consists in visiting all the clients once starting from a given initial orbit, and that \mathbf{x} is a vector of booleans ($x_{i \rightarrow j} = 1$ if the node $i - th$ is connected with the $j - th$ node, $x_{i \rightarrow j} = 0$ otherwise), the constraints can be expressed as follows

$$\mathbf{x}_{lb} = \mathbf{0}_{S \times 1} \quad (11a)$$

$$\mathbf{x}_{ub} = \mathbf{1}_{S \times 1} \quad (11b)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^{N_{sat}} x_{0 \rightarrow j} = 1 \quad (11c)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^S x_j = N_{sat} - 1 \quad (11d)$$

$$1 \leq \sum_{j=i+1}^S x_{i \rightarrow j} \leq 2 \quad \forall i = 1, \dots, N_{sat} - 1 \quad (11e)$$

Equations 11a and 11b impose that the solution has to be composed by booleans, Equation 11c imposes that the node relative to the initial servicer orbit can have only one edge, Equation 11d assures that the number of edges equals $N_{sat} - 1$, Equations 11e assure that, except for the node relative to the initial servicer orbit ($\forall i = 1, \dots, N_{sat} - 1$), each node can be connected to the others at least once and maximum twice (once if the node is the final orbit, twice if it is an intermediate orbit). The set of Equation 11 can be easily converted into matrix form and furnished to the MILP solver. It is important to underline that Equations 11 are not sufficient to find an open tour where all the nodes are connected constituting a continuous sequence. In fact, a solution where clusters of nodes are linked in a closed form can satisfy the constraints not representing a visitation sequence (presence of subtours). To solve this problem, the solution given by the MILP solver must be tightened iteratively by excluding the subtours until a feasible solution is found. An efficient strategy consists in introducing inequality constraints, one per subtour, in order to exclude all possible re-combinations of the nodes of the subtour in the following iteration. The algorithm for the derivation of such inequalities is delineated in Algorithm 1. Finally, the MILP based algorithm to solve the STSP can be written as in Algorithm 2.

Algorithm 1 Subtours Inequality Constraints

- | | |
|--|--|
| 1: Given the $i - th$ iteration solution \mathbf{x}_{opt}^i
2: $N_{ST} \leftarrow$ Number of subtours in \mathbf{x}_{opt}^i
3: $j \leftarrow 1$
4: while $j \leq N_{ST}$ do | 5: $\mathbf{M} \leftarrow$ Indexes of the subtour nodes
6: $N_{edges} \leftarrow$ Number of subtour edges
7: Add $\sum_{z \in \mathbf{M}} x_z \leq N_{edges} - 1$ to constraints
8: $j \leftarrow j + 1$
9: end while |
|--|--|
-

ΔV_{QL} coupling with MILP (MILP/ ΔV_{QL})

Q-law is capable of obtaining near-optimal fuel depletion and time of flight results both for minimum-time and minimum-fuel frameworks. Although Q-law cost computation is relatively fast, its application within the ES algorithm could result in prohibitive computational time when a large dataset is considered. The distance metric of Equation 8 has been coupled with MILP to derive a new algorithm (MILP/ ΔV_{QL}) overcoming

Algorithm 2 MILP based

- | | |
|---|---|
| 1: Define N_{sat} | 7: while $N_{ST} > 1$ do |
| 2: Choose leg cost function $J = J(x_{i \rightarrow j})$ | 8: Add constraints to exclude subtours (Algorithm 1) |
| 3: Compute $\mathbf{w} = [J(x_{0 \rightarrow 1}), \dots, J(x_{N_{sat}-1 \rightarrow N_{sat}})]^T$ | 9: $\mathbf{x}_{opt}^i \leftarrow$ MILP solver i -th solution |
| 4: Write constraints (Equations 11) | 10: Compute number of subtours $N_{ST}(\mathbf{x}_{opt}^i)$ |
| 5: $\mathbf{x}_{opt}^1 \leftarrow$ MILP solver first solution | 11: end while |
| 6: Compute number of subtours $N_{ST}(\mathbf{x}_{opt}^1)$ | |
-

these computational bottlenecks while guaranteeing an accurate estimation in terms of fuel depletion for the five elements targeting transfer. As previously explained, MILP cannot be applied when time and sequence dependencies are included and is based on the computation of the weights vector which does not consider the history of previously visited satellites. Equation 8 has been introduced to derive a distance metric which does not depend on the previously visited clients. Exploiting the symmetry of the ΔV_{QL} distance metric, it is possible to compute and store the weights needed by MILP algorithm in the \mathbf{w}_{QL} vector and the associated Duty Cycles in the \mathbf{DC}_{QL}

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{w}_{QL} &= [\Delta V_{QL}(0, 1), \dots, \Delta V_{QL}(0, N_{sat}), \Delta V_{QL}(1, 2), \dots, \Delta V_{QL}(N_{sat} - 1, N_{sat})]^T \\ \mathbf{DC}_{QL} &= [DC_{QL}(0, 1), \dots, DC_{QL}(0, N_{sat}), DC_{QL}(1, 2), \dots, DC_{QL}(N_{sat} - 1, N_{sat})]^T \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The quantities given by Equations 12 can be used within Mixed Integer Linear Programming framework to initialize the MILP/ ΔV_{QL} algorithm (Algorithm3).

Algorithm 3 MILP/ ΔV_{QL}

- | | |
|---|--|
| 1: Define N_{sat} | 4: Compute and store \mathbf{w}_{QL} and \mathbf{DC}_{QL} vectors (Equations 12) |
| 2: Define Q-law parameters ($W_P, W_{[1:5]}, \bar{\eta}_r, \bar{\eta}_a, \epsilon_{[1:5]}$) | 5: Find the optimal sequence by using Algorithm. 2 |
| 3: Choose minimum-time or minimum-fuel | |
-

Algorithm 3 returns the sequence ($\mathbf{d}_{opt} \in \mathcal{R}^{N_{sat}}$) which minimizes the total ΔV . Once the optimal sequence has been found, it is possible to extract the associated components from the stored vectors \mathbf{w}_{QL} and \mathbf{DC}_{QL} to obtain the costs and Duty Cycles associated to the optimal sequence as

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta \mathbf{V}_{opt}(\mathbf{d}_{opt}) &= [\Delta V_{QL}(0, d_{opt,1}), \dots, \Delta V_{QL}(d_{opt,N_{sat}-1}, d_{opt,N_{sat}})]^T \\ \mathbf{DC}_{opt}(\mathbf{d}_{opt}) &= [DC_{QL}(0, d_{opt,1}), \dots, DC_{QL}(d_{opt,N_{sat}-1}, d_{opt,N_{sat}})]^T \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

where $d_{opt,i}$ represents the i -th component of \mathbf{d}_{opt} . Equations 13 can be used to retrieve mass depletion and time of flight of each transfer for a generic servicer satellite with initial mass m_0 , maximum available thrust T_{max} and specific impulse of the propulsion system I_{sp} . Total fuel consumption Δm and total time of flight TOF of the entire sequence are easily found by summing up the contributions of each leg. The procedure, based on an iterative procedure which updates the servicer mass during the trajectory, is reported in Algorithm 4.

Algorithm 4 MILP/ ΔV_{QL} Δm and TOF computation

- | | |
|--|---|
| 1: $m_1 \leftarrow m_0$ | 6: $f_i \leftarrow \frac{T_{max}}{0.5(m_i + m_{i+1})} DC_{opt,i}$ |
| 2: $TOF \leftarrow 0$ | 7: $TOF \leftarrow TOF + \frac{\Delta V_{opt,i}}{f_i}$ |
| 3: $i \leftarrow 1$ | 8: $i \leftarrow i + 1$ |
| 4: while $i \leq N_{sat}$ do | 9: end while |
| 5: $m_{i+1} \leftarrow m_i \left(1 - e^{-\frac{\Delta V_{opt,i}}{90 I_{sp}}} \right)$ | 10: $\Delta m \leftarrow m_0 - m_i$ |
-

f_i represents an estimation of the average acceleration available during the $i - th$ transfer. In this form, MILP/ ΔV_{QL} maintains the possibility to accurately estimate mass depletion and time of flight the Q-law would return if evaluated on the same sequence with a specific servicer satellite. The introduction of the Equation 9 is meant to apply the methodology also in the minimum-fuel context. The computational bottlenecks associated with a large dataset are solved by reducing the number of Q-law evaluation to only $S = (N_{sat} + 1)N_{sat}/2$.

RESULTS AND SIMULATIONS

The distance metrics $\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}$ and ΔV_{QL} have been applied in combination with both ES and MILP resulting in four approaches (ES/ $\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}$, MILP/ $\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}$, ES/ ΔV_{QL} and MILP/ ΔV_{QL}) to solve the STSP. The algorithms have been initially tested and compared on a subset of 12 LEO debris from the IRIDIUM-33 collision.¹⁵ The initial orbital elements are reported in Table 1. A sequence $\mathbf{d} = [d_0, d_1, \dots, d_{N_{sat}}]$ is considered feasible when, the servicer, starting from a given initial orbit, visits all the clients only once. The cost of each maneuver (leg) between two objects of the sequence (d_i, d_{i+1}) is quantified by a distance metric $C(d_i, d_{i+1})$, while the cost of the entire sequence is the sum of all legs $J(\mathbf{d}) = C(d_0, d_1) + \sum_{i=1}^{N_{sat}-1} C(d_i, d_{i+1})$. The optimal sequence \mathbf{d}_{opt} is given by $\mathbf{d}_{opt} = \mathbf{d} : \min J(\mathbf{d})$.

In a multiple-satellite-visit problem, main constraints are usually given by the maximum quantity of fuel the servicer can embark (i.e., the more fuel available the more clients can be visited), by the maximum time to complete the tour, or by a combination of both. When constraints are considered, the optimal tour is represented by the feasible visiting sequence which minimizes J and satisfies the constraints. In this paper, the cost is quantified through the increment in velocity ΔV needed. The total time of flight and fuel consumption of the solution can be computed a posteriori from the ΔV once servicer inertial and propulsion system properties have been assigned (initial mass m_0 , specific impulse I_{sp} and maximum thrust T_{max}) to check the satisfaction of the constraints for a real scenario. It is important to underline that the methodologies presented in this work are general and can be used to find the optimal visiting tour according to criteria different from the minimization of the fuel.

Table 1. Servicer and Clients Initial Keplerian Elements

ID	a [m]	e	i [rad]	ω [rad]	Ω [rad]
Servicer - 0	7164040.5518	0.0019	1.5079	0.8909	2.8765
Client - 1	6989199.3166	0.0030	1.5081	2.1655	2.6417
Client - 2	7148540.2308	0.0025	1.5081	1.0069	2.8457
Client - 3	7159283.7674	0.0017	1.5075	0.8765	2.7557
Client - 4	7163255.1260	0.0020	1.5082	1.0466	3.0286
Client - 5	7123773.3419	0.0020	1.5077	3.2640	2.6863
Client - 6	7105550.2633	0.0057	1.5027	3.1392	1.3450
Client - 7	7142543.1535	0.0033	1.5070	0.9020	2.5723
Client - 8	7312321.2253	0.0256	1.5011	2.1126	2.2211
Client - 9	7048230.6726	0.0019	1.5049	2.3550	1.0898
Client - 10	7078633.3020	0.0010	1.5068	3.8077	3.4273
Client - 11	6945287.2368	0.0021	1.5033	6.0589	0.1315
Client - 12	7127598.3265	0.0058	1.5070	0.4993	2.6333

ES/ $\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}$ and MILP/ $\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}$ Results

Table 2 provides the results obtained by using the ES/ $\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}$ and MILP/ $\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}$ in terms of optimal sequence (sequence minimizing the sum of ΔV s), total cost and CPU time. Results are reported for an increasing number of clients in order to show the behavior of computational cost. Notably, the two algorithms found the same optimal sequence and total cost. The MILP/ $\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}$ algorithm outperforms the ES/ $\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}$ algorithm in terms of computational time. It is self-evident how enumerating all possible sequences becomes prohibitively expensive even when analytic cost functions are used. On the opposite, the CPU time needed by

MILP/ $\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}$ algorithm is weakly dependent on the dataset size, making this method particularly suitable in the case of a high number of clients. It is remarkable how the derivation of the problem into MILP context drastically reduces the CPU time results present in literature (see Reference 15) that were found by using an analytic distance metric simpler than $\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}$ and an Exhaustive Search. It is important to underline how

Table 2. Optimal Sequence, Total Cost and CPU Time comparison for $\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}$ using ES and MILP

N_{sat}	Optimal Sequence	ΔV [km/s]	ES CPU Time [s]	MILP CPU Time [s]
1	[0,1]	2.7487	8.27e-3	6.25e-2
2	[0,2,1]	2.7533	8.38e-3	6.25e-2
3	[0,2,3,1]	2.7556	1.21e-2	4.68e-2
4	[0,4,2,3,1]	6.3023	1.37e-2	7.81e-2
5	[0,4,2,3,5,1]	6.3024	1.40e-2	7.81e-2
6	[0,4,2,3,5,1,6]	19.090	2.29e-2	4.69e-2
7	[0,4,2,3,5,1,7,6]	19.394	8.27e-2	6.25e-2
8	[0,4,2,3,5,1,7,8,6]	20.588	6.19e-1	6.25e-2
9	[0,4,2,3,5,1,7,8,6,9]	23.570	5.79	4.69e-2
10	[0,4,10,2,3,5,1,7,8,6,9]	32.629	64.6	7.81e-2
11	[0,4,10,2,3,5,1,7,8,6,9,11]	42.933	776	6.25e-2
12	[0,4,10,2,3,5,1,12,7,8,6,9,11]	42.955	1.02e4	6.25e-2

the optimal sequences are characterized by a succession of clients with increasing Ω . This behavior, called *RAAN walk*, was firstly found by Izzo et al.¹⁶ and constitutes a simple heuristic for a first guess solution. This aspect is coherent with the fact that RAAN correction requires a large amount of fuel.

ES/ ΔV_{QL} results

Table 3 reports the inertial and low-thrust propulsion system properties used in the simulations involving the Q-law. The NEXT ion thruster was chosen, it has a high maximum thrust of 0.276 N and an high specific impulse of 4170 s.³² These values, when associated with the specific strategy (i.e., minimum-time Q-law or minimum-fuel Q-law), provide estimates of both the fuel consumption and the time of flights of each leg of the sequence. Q-law weights (W_P , $W_{[1:5]}$) and stopping criteria tolerances ($\epsilon_{[1:5]}$) used in the simulations are

Table 3. Inertial and Low-thrust Propulsion System Properties

Initial Mass m_0 [kg]	Specific Impulse I_{sp} [s]	Maximum Thrust T_{max} [N]
700	4170	0.276

reported in Table 4 (a_f and e_f indicate that stopping criteria tolerances on semi-major axis and eccentricity were set as a percentage of the targeted values). In case of minimum-fuel Q-law, relative and absolute effectivities thresholds were set as $\bar{\eta}_r = 0.2$ and $\bar{\eta}_a = 0.2$. A change in these parameters can improve convergence and both fuel consumption and time of flight obtained by the Q-law. This aspect has not been considered in this work. Q-law was integrated using adaptive Runge-Kutta78 in order to reduce computational time while maintaining a good precision. Table 5 reports the results obtained with ES/ ΔV_{QL} in terms of fuel

Table 4. Q-law Weights and Stopping Criteria Tolerances

W_P	$W_{[1:5]}$	ϵ_1 [m]	ϵ_2	ϵ_3 [rad]	ϵ_4 [rad]	ϵ_5 [rad]
1	[1, 2, 2, 1, 1]	0.01 a_f	0.1 e_f	0.0017	0.0017	0.017

consumption and total time of flight. Fuel consumption and total time of flights are not positive monotonic for the all simulations with respect to the increase of the number of clients. This behavior is due to the fact that the dataset contains clusters of clients (i.e., clients 1,2 and 3 and clients 4 and 5) with similar Keplerian

elements, in particular inclinations and RAANs. This aspect could change when convergence tolerances become more stringent. On the other hand, when clients whose inclinations and RAANs differ significantly with respect to the others are included (i.e., clients 4 and 6), fuel consumption and time of flight increase significantly. The behavior is coherent with the fact that the most expensive maneuvers are those meant to correct inclination and RAAN differences. ΔV of optimal sequences found by the Q-law are coherent with those reported in Table 2 since both distance metrics consider the minimization of the time strategy. Slight differences are present mainly because ΔV_{QL} distance metric enables a five elements targeting (e and ω are included) instead of three. Since the initial clients orbits are nearly circular slight increase in the cost can be expected. This behavior is not always valid because of user defined tolerances which stops the integration when the servicer does not reach exactly the client orbit. If the Q-law adopts the minimum-fuel strategy by

Table 5. Optimal Sequence, Cost, TOF and CPU Time of Q-law using ES

N_{sat}	Optimal Sequence	Minimum-time				Minimum-fuel			
		ΔV [km/s]	Δm [kg]	TOF [days]	CPU Time [s]	ΔV [km/s]	Δm [kg]	TOF [days]	CPU Time [s]
1	[0,1]	2.7260	45.45	77.97	1.44	2.3824	39.67	81.27	2.28
2	[0,2,1]	2.7622	45.71	78.53	2.41	2.4311	39.73	81.07	3.81
3	[0,2,3,1]	2.7650	45.48	78.20	6.34	2.4099	40.37	81.14	11.7
4	[0,4,2,3,1]	6.2821	99.67	171.2	23.6	5.5224	88.38	177.9	70.6
5	[0,4,2,3,5,1]	6.2910	99.64	171.2	114	5.5282	88.78	178.6	397
6	[0,4,2,3,5,1,6]	19.754	267.9	453.8	1.87e3	17.289	243.1	554.8	7.73e3
7	[0,4,2,3,5,1,7,6]	20.198	268.9	461.7	1.27e4	17.538	247.2	556.9	5.53e4

the inclusion of effectivity thresholds, the solutions present a reduction of the fuel expended at the cost of an increase in the time of flight. The result is coherent with the fact that the thrust is turned off at points where it is less convenient to maneuver the servicer (coast arcs). CPU Time also increases because of computational evaluation of the effectivities at current position through a Grid Search algorithm and comparison with the thresholds. It is evident that the computational time increases quickly when a larger number of visitations is considered. This aspect limits the application of ES/ ΔV_{QL} algorithm when $N_{sat} \geq 8$. MILP/ ΔV_{QL} algorithm has been developed to overcome these computational bottlenecks. However, optimal sequences found by ES/ ΔV_{QL} (both minimum-time and minimum-fuel) up to seven satellites case are identical to those obtained by ES/ $\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}$ and MILP/ $\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}$; this validates the ability of the analytic cost function to quantify the visitation sequence with a good accuracy. The advantages of ΔV_{QL} lie in the possibility of estimating the cost in the more general case of elliptical orbits since an analytic function for the five elements targeting is not present in the literature. In addition, the minimum-fuel version of the Q-law makes it possible to consider scenarios where the servicer depletes less fuel to visit all the clients.

MILP/ ΔV_{QL} results

Table 6 reports the results obtained with MILP/ ΔV_{QL} in the minimum-time and minimum-fuel contexts using the same data reported in Tables 3 and 4. MILP/ ΔV_{QL} is able to find results even when the dataset consists of a high number of satellites to visit within a reasonable computational time. All possible transfer costs are quantified by using Equations 12, then MILP solver is run to find the optimal sequence and finally Algorithm 4 is applied to estimate fuel consumption and time of flight starting from the obtained ΔV_s and DC_s (Equation 13). Once the optimal sequence has been found by MILP/ ΔV_{QL} , the results are compared with the Q-law (Table 7) evaluated on the same sequence. Table 7 reports only the results for $N_{sat} \geq 8$. The similarity of the results both in terms of increment in velocity, fuel consumption and time of flight shows how MILP/ ΔV_{QL} can be implemented to avoid the evaluation of all possible sequence without reducing the accuracy of the estimations. As in ES/ ΔV_{QL} algorithm, MILP/ ΔV_{QL} applied in the minimum-fuel context presents smaller fuel consumption but higher time of flight and computational cost. Some crucial aspects emerge from the results obtained in the twelve clients simulations. Considering MILP/ ΔV_{QL} in the minimum-time context, the twelve satellites optimal tour requires 467.9 [kg] of propellant and 804.8

[days]. Low-thrust technology allows a mission of this kind to be feasible (i.e., if High Thrust technology was employed in the same scenario, the amount of fuel embarked on the servicer would increase consistently). On the other hand, very low control accelerations require a longer time of flight to perform all visitations that cannot be compatible with the time constraints of the mission. If a long time mission does not represent a problem, the fuel expended can be lowered by adopting MILP/ ΔV_{QL} in the minimum-fuel context (435.43 [kg]). Thanks to the fast computation of MILP/ ΔV_{QL} , a trade-off analysis can be performed by tuning effectivity thresholds. Depending on mission constraints, the most suitable solution can be chosen among the obtained trajectories. Also in this case, optimal sequences found by MILP/ ΔV_{QL} for all possible N_{sat} are the same as those obtained by ES/ $\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}$ and MILP/ $\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}$. Figure 1 plots the results reported in Table 5, 6, 7

Table 6. Optimal Sequence, Cost, TOF and CPU Time Comparison of Q-law using MILP

N_{sat}	Optimal Sequence	Minimum-time				Minimum-fuel			
		ΔV [km/s]	Δm [kg]	TOF [days]	CPU Time [s]	ΔV [km/s]	Δm [kg]	TOF [days]	CPU Time [s]
1	[0,1]	2.7260	45.45	77.97	2.35	2.3824	39.67	81.27	5.91
2	[0,2,1]	2.7465	45.12	77.39	6.89	2.3622	39.20	80.47	13.6
3	[0,2,3,1]	2.7092	44.76	76.76	8.66	2.4254	39.85	79.54	19.6
4	[0,4,2,3,1]	6.2755	99.16	170.1	12.6	5.4721	87.78	177.6	36.6
5	[0,4,2,3,5,1]	6.2514	98.91	169.6	15.6	5.4468	87.61	177.4	50.7
6	[0,4,2,3,5,1,6]	19.713	264.1	455.7	39.5	16.943	242.5	567.8	194
7	[0,4,2,3,5,1,7,6]	20.056	268.3	462.3	47.9	17.121	246.4	559.4	283
8	[0,4,2,3,5,1,7,8,6]	22.628	287.8	494.9	66.9	19.072	260.6	583.8	320
9	[0,4,2,3,5,1,7,8,6,9]	25.641	316.8	544.6	99.9	21.667	287.6	639.0	533
10	[0,4,10,2,3,5,1,7,8,6,9]	34.241	394.1	677.4	128	29.224	359.0	794.3	696
11	[0,4,10,2,3,5,1,7,8,6,9,11]	46.102	467.8	804.5	182	39.367	435.1	976.3	1.04e3
12	[0,4,10,2,3,5,1,12,7,8,6,9,11]	46.120	467.9	804.8	203	39.422	435.4	977.3	1.42e3

Table 7. Total Cost and Total TOF of Q-law Applied to the Sequence Found by MILP/ ΔV_{QL}

N_{sat}	Optimal Sequence	Minimum-time			Minimum-fuel		
		ΔV [km/s]	Δm [kg]	TOF [days]	ΔV [km/s]	Δm [kg]	TOF [days]
8	[0,4,2,3,5,1,7,8,6]	21.656	287.8	494.1	19.415	264.2	575.9
9	[0,4,2,3,5,1,7,8,6,9]	24.648	317.2	544.5	22.065	291.7	631.5
10	[0,4,10,2,3,5,1,7,8,6,9]	33.843	394.9	677.9	30.415	364.9	785.1
11	[0,4,10,2,3,5,1,7,8,6,9,11]	45.032	467.2	802.5	41.261	440.1	969.2
12	[0,4,10,2,3,5,1,12,7,8,6,9,11]	45.154	467.9	803.3	41.750	440.4	980.8

in terms of total fuel consumption and TOF for both minimum-time and minimum-fuel strategies. Algorithm 4 post-processes the results obtained by MILP/ ΔV_{QL} to pass from optimal ΔV_s and DC_s to mass depletion and time of flight. It accurately reproduces the same results obtained by the classical implementation of the Q-law. When MILP/ ΔV_{QL} is coupled with Algorithm 4, STSP can be quickly solved without a significant precision loss.

Figure 1. Δm and TOF algorithms comparison

Figure 2. ΔV comparison

Optimal ΔV_s comparison

Figure 2 shows the ΔV_s found by the different algorithms for an increasing number of clients (as the optimal sequence is the same for all the simulations). Up to seven clients, MILP/ ΔV_{QL} presents similar results with respect to those obtained by ES/ ΔV_{QL} in both minimum-time and minimum-fuel scenarios indicating that optimal sequence and the associated cost can be quickly obtained if the problem is transcribed into a form suitable for MILP solvers. Cost curve obtained by $\Delta V_{Ed,\Omega}$ is below the one referred to MILP/ ΔV_{QL} in the minimum-time context. This is in accordance with the fact that ΔV_{QL} takes also into account the cost for eccentricity and argument of perigee corrections. Minimum-fuel MILP/ ΔV_{QL} curve clearly indicates the possibility to reduce fuel consumption needed to visit all the clients of a given sequence. Even if it has not been shown by the simulations, this aspect could also affect the optimal tour sequence. Finally, all the curves report significant steps at the same N_{sat} caused by the inclusion of clients whose orbital elements differ consistently with respect to those considered before.

MILP/ ΔV_{QL} results for $N_{sat} = 20$

This section is intended to show how it is possible to obtain the optimal tour and the trajectory of a servicer visiting twenty clients in a reasonable time by using the MILP/ ΔV_{QL} algorithm. The Q-law user defined parameters, inertial and propulsion system properties of the servicer and its initial orbit are the same used in previous simulations. Eight new clients (Table 8) from the IRIDIUM-33 collision have been added to those reported in Table 1. Table 9 reports the results of the simulations in the minimum-time and minimum-fuel

Table 8. Clients Initial Keplerian Elements

ID	a [m]	e	i [rad]	ω [rad]	Ω [rad]
Client - 13	7064040.5518	0.0019	1.5279	0.6765	0.9909
Client - 14	6988199.3166	0.0030	1.5481	0.5417	2.1655
Client - 15	7144540.2308	0.0025	1.5181	4.8457	1.3069
Client - 16	7159883.7674	0.0017	1.4875	5.5557	1.8765
Client - 17	7163295.1260	0.0020	1.4982	4.1286	2.0466
Client - 18	7125673.3419	0.0020	1.5277	2.6863	3.0640
Client - 19	7305550.2633	0.0057	1.5627	1.5450	3.0392
Client - 20	7102543.1535	0.0033	1.4370	2.7723	2.9020

context. In both cases, the optimal sequence is the same and the servicer visits all the clients in less than three years with the propulsion system considered. In this paper, time of servicing has not been considered but it can be easily taken into account. Fuel expended is 84.5% and 80.2% of the initial mass respectively for the minimum-time and minimum-fuel case. If the servicer can not embark with this amount of propellant, fewer clients can be visited. minimum-time simulation is five times faster but computational run-times remain limited in all cases. Figure 3 shows a graph visualization of the optimal tour in the (Ω, i) . Nodes represent satellites and their coordinates correspond to their initial RAAN and inclination. In particular, the node in red represents the servicer initial state while in blue those of the clients. Edges represent the transfer maneuvers of the optimal sequence and colors are assigned according to the ΔV_s (only minimum-time case color map is shown). The ID relative to each of the satellites is reported and a zoom of the initial transfers is present (top-right) for clarity. Graph visualization better shows how the servicer firstly visit satellites with similar

Table 9. Optimal Sequence, Cost, TOF and CPU Time Comparison of Q-law using MILP $N_{sat} = 20$

	Optimal Sequence	ΔV [km/s]	Δm [kg]	TOF [days]	CPU Time [s]
Minimum-time	[0,4,2,20,3,5,18,1,12,7,8,19,6,9,13,14,11,16,15,17,10]	76.217	591.4	1016	312
Minimum-fuel	[0,4,2,20,3,5,18,1,12,7,8,19,6,9,13,14,11,16,15,17,10]	66.265	561.5	1213	1.57e3

Figure 3. Optimal sequence in the (Ω, i) plan

RAAN. Apart from the first transfer (from 0 to 4), the optimal tour follows the *RAAN walk* heuristic. In fact, the succession of visited clients is characterized by a monotonically decreasing RAAN with respect to that of the initial servicer location. This behavior could be not respected in case of larger differences in inclination between the satellites (i.e., inclination correction maneuver costs would be more expensive and comparable with respect to RAAN correction ones). It is also visible how expensive maneuvers are performed in the final phase of the tour (except for the transfer from client 8 to client 19 whose orbits present a larger difference in inclination). This behavior is probably maintained even if the optimal sequence is selected according to a minimization of total Δm criteria. Servicer would tend to visit near clients first and furthest clients later because of the increase in maximum available control acceleration. Figure 4 shows

Figure 4. Optimal tour orbital elements convergence

the servicer orbital elements trajectory for the optimal sequence for the minimum-time case (minimum-fuel case does not present appreciable differences). Clients' Keplerian elements are horizontal lines because of the assumptions previously made. Servicer trajectory is shown in black while red dots represent the end

Figure 5. Trajectory from client 11 to client 16

of each transfer maneuver. Elongations of the semi-major axis and eccentricities are present, mainly in the last phase of the tour. This behavior characterizes the Q-law feedback controller²⁶ and typically is present when the transfer requires a great correction of the RAAN. Changing Ω and i is cheaper when the satellite is maneuvered at greater semi-major axis. In order to minimize the time needed to enlarge the orbit, the controller increases the eccentricity exploiting the apogee phases to steer the thrust with a greater out-of-plane component which mainly acts on RAAN and inclination changes. Ω history plot remarks the fact that clients are visited following a descending orbit plane rotation with respect to servicer initial RAAN. Figure 5 shows a plot of the servicer trajectory when it is maneuvered from client 11 to 16 in cartesian coordinates. The left figure refers to minimum-time case where the thrust is always on and the right figure refers to minimum-fuel case where also coast arcs are present (in red). Elongation of the semi-major axis and eccentricity can be better appreciated in both plots. The shape of the curve does not differ significantly between minimum-time and minimum-fuel cases except for the distance between two adjacent revolutions (right plot presents a narrower inter-revolution distance). In fact, coast arcs mechanism minimizes fuel consumption but slows the convergence to final orbit thus requiring a greater number of revolutions.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have solved the optimal tour planning of a low-thrust multiple-visitation problem using different algorithms. The general problem statement has been reported and assumptions have been made to turn it into a standard *Travelling Salesman Problem*. Two distance metrics have been used to quantify the cost of orbit-to-orbit maneuvers. The first, present in literature, is based on an analytic function derived using Edelbaum's theory formalism and accounts for circular-to-circular transfer. The second, derived in this paper for the first time, exploits the Q-law feedback controller to derive a near-optimal ΔV distance metric which estimates the cost of a five orbital element targeting maneuver. The global optimal visiting sequence has been firstly obtained by Exhaustive Search for both distance metrics. Computational time has been drastically reduced by translating the problem into the Mixed Integer Linear Programming formalism. A variable size LEO satellites dataset (up to twelve satellites), taken from IRIDIUM-33 collision data, has been used to test the different approaches. All the algorithms found the same optimal visiting sequence and slightly different results in terms of total cost. Mixed Integer Programming implementation reduced CPU time by six orders of magnitude when the analytic distance metric is employed and allowed to enlarge the range of applicability of the slower, but more accurate, Q-law based distance metric. The novelty of coupling the Q-law based distance metric and Mixed Integer Linear Programming description resulted into a fast and versatile algorithm. Its main advantages have been shown for an enlarged twenty LEO satellite dataset. Additional key aspects are the possibility to account for a minimum-fuel transfer maneuver cost estimation,

to reconstruct the entire trajectory and control law and to obtain information such as fuel mass depletion and time of flight for a specific low-thrust propulsion system. These additional data can prove useful during the design process of a mission subject to multiple constraints. All the approaches reported in this paper have been applied to the particular case where the servicer is required to visit all the clients only once starting from a given initial orbit. However, they can be adopted to solve general multiple-visitation problems by applying small variations.

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